

Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Health Sector

A 2030 Outlook

by Ompe Aime Mudimu (TH Köln, Germany)

Abstract

This white paper addresses the critical role of healthcare providers, specifically Emergency Medical Services (EMS) and hospitals, in ensuring public safety and supporting critical infrastructure during emergencies. It highlights the increasing complexity of health crises, such as pandemics, terrorism, natural disasters, and cyber threats, that strain healthcare systems across the European Union. Key vulnerabilities include limited resources, time constraints during emergencies, and dependencies on other critical infrastructures such as power and telecommunications.

The paper emphasizes the need for enhanced resilience and interoperability within healthcare systems. It explores current challenges, gaps in preparedness, and limitations in disaster response, using the COVID-19 pandemic as a case study to reveal significant weaknesses in emergency response systems. Solutions are discussed through the analysis of various EU projects, which focus on strengthening decision support systems, increasing collaboration between healthcare providers and community actors, and improving real-time data utilization for crisis management.

Furthermore, the white paper underscores the importance of standardizing emergency protocols across regions, integrating advanced technology for preparedness, and fostering continuous training for healthcare personnel. The conclusion calls for sustained investments and political commitment to harmonize fragmented healthcare systems across the EU, thus enhancing their capacity to respond effectively to future crises.

1. Introduction

The following Figure 1 illustrates the structure of the document, which is divided into two main sections: “Hospitals and Clinics” and “Emergency Services”. At the center of the diagram is “Health,” representing the overarching category that connects various entities and institutions within the healthcare system.

The document follows this structure and focuses on the two key areas of healthcare provision: Hospitals and Clinics, responsible for general medical care, and Emergency Services, which are dedicated to addressing acute and life-threatening situations.

Figure 1: The Health Sector with a Focus on Healthcare Providers

Importance:

Strong and resilient healthcare networks are the cornerstone of an effective state and local emergency response. An efficient and well-structured Emergency Medical Services (EMS) system provides critical skills necessary to handle disasters. EMS, often the first line of defense in emergency situations, play a vital role in safeguarding public health.^{1 2}

Situation:

The number of health threats is on the rise. Public health crises are becoming increasingly complex, with the potential for terrorist events, ongoing natural disasters impacting larger and more diverse communities, and the emergence of novel pandemics. These developments present challenges in areas such as personal preparedness, communication, risk management, and organizational mobilization.^{3 4 5}

Therefore:

To be truly prepared for emergencies, public health systems must be able to effectively perform various response capabilities. These include surveillance, epidemiologic investigation, laboratory testing, disease prevention and mitigation, surge capacity for healthcare services, and risk communication to the public. Additionally, the overall system response must be coordinated through an effective incident management approach.⁶

¹ U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2015).

² Liapis, A. et al. (2015), p. 208.

³ Lawton, L. (2013), p. 144.

⁴ Liapis, A. et al. (2015), p. 206.

⁵ Hoepfner, M.M./Olson, D.K./Larson, S.C. (2010), p. 25.

⁶ Biddinger, P.D. et al. (2010), p. 101ff.

1.1 The Emergency Services Sector: Overview and Importance

The Emergency Services Sector (ESS) is made up of highly skilled personnel, both paid and volunteer, along with physical and cyber resources that provide a wide range of essential activities. These activities include prevention, protection, mitigation, response, and recovery efforts, which are geographically distributed across federal, state, local, tribal, and territorial levels of government, as well as private-sector resources.

Given its role as the first line of defense for nearly all critical infrastructure sectors, the ESS is vital to national security. A disruption or failure within the sector could lead to severe consequences, such as loss of life, public health crises, long-term economic damage, and cascading disruptions to other critical infrastructures. While the sector is diversified in terms of organization and mission, making a complete shutdown difficult, any damage to its key components could severely affect public safety and infrastructure protection.^{7 8}

Figure 2: Emergency Services in the Health Sector

⁷ Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (n.d.).

⁸ U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2015).

The ESS is composed of different sectors according to CISA⁹. The four most relevant, illustrated in Figure 2, are:

Emergency Management

Emergency management involves the strategic application of resources to mitigate, prevent, protect against, and respond to all threats and hazards. It operates across all levels of government and the private sector, and its specialized capabilities include emergency planning and response coordination. In some countries, National Guard or Home Guard military units are key components of emergency management, providing critical support during large-scale emergencies or natural disasters.

Emergency Medical Services (EMS)

EMS provides pre-hospital, emergency medical care and coordinates the response and transport of victims. It operates at various government levels and in the private sector. EMS personnel, often volunteers or paid professionals, include specialized teams for air and water transport as well as ambulance services.

Fire and Rescue Services

Fire and Rescue Services respond to both natural and man-made disasters, such as earthquakes, hazmat spills, and fires. Their responsibilities include fire suppression, prevention, and public safety education. They can be found in both the public and private sectors and are often staffed by volunteers. Specialized capabilities include technical rescue, vehicle extraction, and air and marine fire suppression.

Law Enforcement

Law enforcement maintains public safety by enforcing laws, investigating criminal activities, and managing public order. Found at all levels of government and in the private sector, their specialized units include bomb squads, tactical teams, crime scene investigation, and air and marine units. While private sector law enforcement exist, they do not possess the same legal authority or enforcement powers as public law enforcement agencies.

1.2 Focused elements of the Health Sector

The focus of this paper is on "health providers" with a primary emphasis on EMS and hospitals, which will be further discussed in the following.

Emergency Medical Service

In the European Union, there are numerous diverse emergency healthcare systems. Emergency Medical Service (EMS) is the first line of defense for almost all critical infrastructure sectors. The most important asset in this system is the personnel who face the same risks as other critical infrastructure sectors. Any damage or disruption to EMS components can severely hinder the protection of the public, other critical infrastructure sectors, and disciplines within the sector.^{10 11}

⁹ Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (n.d.).

¹⁰ F. Beltrame/P. Maryni/G. Orsi (1998), p. 89.

¹¹ Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (n.d.).

Hospitals

Hospital emergency response planning is critical for ensuring the continuity of healthcare services during disasters. Key components include¹²:

- a) **Command and Control Systems:** Establishing a hospital incident command group that involves essential services, such as hospital administration, communications, and nursing administration.
- b) **Communication:** Clear, accurate, and timely communication ensures informed decision-making and effective cooperation across various hospital departments.
- c) **Safety and Security:** Ensuring the physical and psychological safety of patients and staff is critical.
- d) **Triage:** Efficient patient organization is essential to prioritize care.
- e) **Surge Capacity:** Expanding hospital capacity to meet an increased demand for clinical care is necessary during large-scale emergencies.
- f) **Continuity of Essential Services:** Maintaining essential services such as emergency care, maternal health, and urgent operations ensures that critical care continues even during disasters (Hospital emergency response checklist, WHO).
- g) **Human Resources Management:** Managing staff resources to ensure adequate capacity during a crisis.
- h) **Logistics and Supply Chain Management:** Ensuring the availability of necessary medical supplies and equipment.
- i) **Post-Disaster Recovery Planning:** Implementing recovery measures to mitigate the long-term impact of disasters.

2. Challenges, Gaps and Limitations

As outlined in Chapter 1, the Health Sector is indispensable in safeguarding critical infrastructures, acting as the first line of defense in emergencies that affect these infrastructures. A failure in healthcare services makes other critical infrastructures more vulnerable and significantly hinders recovery efforts. For instance, if a power plant's basement floods, Fire and Rescue Services would provide the pumps and personnel to prevent damage. However, if the fire department itself is incapacitated, this delays recovery, leading to prolonged power outages affecting both the population and industries. Consequently, it is part of the collection of critical infrastructures and is threatened by similar dangers. Figure 3 summarizes the significant threats to the health sector. In addition to threats like pandemics,

¹² World Health Organization/Regional Office for Europe (2011).

hospitals and emergency services must contend with extreme weather events, terrorism, cyber threats, and technical failures.

Figure 3, *Evolving Threats to Critical Infrastructures*¹³

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the health sector's vulnerability, revealing critical gaps in emergency preparedness and response. These risks are compounded by the unique challenges that the health sector faces, such as time-sensitive emergencies and limited resources.

First and foremost, there are inherent time constraints during emergencies¹⁴. In emergency situations, the window for effective intervention is often extremely narrow. For example, a stroke patient must receive treatment within a critical 'golden hour' to prevent permanent damage, which places immense pressure on both EMS and hospital staff to respond swiftly. To accomplish these tasks, a substantial supply of human and material resources is necessary, which are naturally limited. This gap between demand and available resources manifests in three major limitations:

1. Quantity of resources,
2. Time constraints in responding,
3. Quality of care provided¹⁵.

For instance, in a mass casualty incident, local healthcare providers may be overwhelmed by the number of affected individuals (=Quantity). Depending on the incident, many people may need urgent treatment (=time constraints). The treatment must be state-of-the-art in terms of materials used and actions performed to achieve the best possible outcome (=Quality).

Aside from these inherent challenges, the health sector is also dependent on other critical infrastructures. Due to globalization and digitalization, there is an increasing interconnection between critical infrastructure sectors and their entities. This is particularly true for the health sector. During the COVID-19 pandemic, power outages or communication failures severely hampered hospitals' ability to maintain ventilators and communicate test results in real-time, underscoring how dependent healthcare is on utilities like electricity and telecommunications. Healthcare institutions can only prepare for incidents to a limited extent, making them

¹³ U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2013), p. 8.

¹⁴ Liapis, A. et al. (2015), p. 205.

¹⁵ Liapis, A. et al. (2015), p. 207.

vulnerable to breakdowns. The COVID-19 pandemic not only revealed the dependency of healthcare on other critical infrastructures but also exposed gaps in emergency preparedness. Many European countries struggled to implement existing pandemic plans effectively. The European Union's healthcare systems are diverse, shaped by each country's political, legal, and technological environment. Addressing the fragmentation arising from the EU's diverse legal, ethical, and technological frameworks will require substantial investment, as well as a strong political commitment to harmonize standards and protocols across member states. Addressing these issues is crucial for improving the overall effectiveness of disaster response and recovery efforts¹⁶. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed critical vulnerabilities and underscored the need for improved coordination and standardization across Europe's fragmented healthcare systems.

In addition to these challenges, hospitals must contend with daily issues such as emergency department overcrowding, a rising uninsured population, and an aging population¹⁷. These factors and others have created an unappealing work environment, leading to a shortage of healthcare workers across Europe, which was exacerbated during the COVID-19 crisis¹⁸.

Similar issues apply to Emergency Medical Services. Volunteering is critical in disaster response, yet organized volunteering is declining. This raises the challenge of engaging citizens in civil organizations rather than relying on spontaneous efforts, which can lead to chaos and inefficiency. Governments must find ways to reverse this trend, as relying on spontaneous volunteering during emergencies can lead to inefficiencies and even chaos. Additionally, trust in government response is lower in the health sector compared to other services like police or firefighters, making it vital to improve transparency and build stronger relationships with the public¹⁹. As emergency organizations grow in responsibility, it is crucial to have the necessary manpower to meet the needs.

The healthcare sector faces numerous challenges, ranging from time-sensitive emergencies and staffing shortages to dependencies on other critical infrastructures. Addressing these issues is key to strengthening the resilience of the health sector, which in turn, bolsters the protection of other critical infrastructures.

3. Solutions and Trends

The preceding chapter highlighted several critical challenges in healthcare, including the increasing complexity of public health crises, the strain on emergency medical services, and the vulnerability of healthcare infrastructure. These problems, which have been exacerbated by recent global events, underscore the urgent need for more resilient and adaptable healthcare systems. In this chapter, several key projects will be presented that focus on strategies to enhance preparedness, interoperability, and the overall capacity of healthcare systems to respond effectively to future crises.

One of the most pressing challenges today is the growing threat of cyber- and cyberphysical-attacks on healthcare systems. Due to the sensitive personal data they handle and their

¹⁶ F. Beltrame/P. Maryni/G. Orsi (1998), p. 89.

¹⁷ Liapis, A. et al. (2015), p. 208.

¹⁸ European Commission (n. D.).

¹⁹ Elkady, S. et al. (2022), p. 18.

reliance on robust digital infrastructure, healthcare services are highly vulnerable. SAFECARE²⁰ project addresses this challenge by integrating physical and cyber security systems to protect healthcare infrastructures. Key aspects of the project include the analysis of threats, support for decision-making, and raising awareness among healthcare providers to create a more secure environment. The project also emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach to managing the interdependencies between critical infrastructures, which requires effective collaboration among key stakeholders.²¹

An excellent example of these interdependencies is water supply in healthcare. NOWATER²², a German research project, focuses on managing the water supply and wastewater disposal for hospitals during crises. By analyzing the risks associated with potential failures in water supply, NOWATER has developed technical and organizational strategies that allow hospitals to maintain critical operations during emergencies. This project highlighted gaps in the preparedness of hospitals in Germany, and as a result, created a practical guide for emergency preparedness and crisis management, which could serve as a model for healthcare facilities across Europe.²³

As mentioned in Chapter 2, the healthcare sector must not only contend with evolving threats to critical infrastructures but also with the challenge of limited resources and time constraints during crises. This is where decision support systems (DSS) can play a pivotal role. The IMPRESS²⁴ project, for example, developed a DSS that integrates real-time data to enhance the operational capabilities of health services during emergencies. The system supports end-to-end crisis management, facilitating better-coordinated responses based on accurate, timely information. This tool addresses the growing need for data-driven decision-making in the face of emergencies, ensuring a more efficient and effective response.²⁵

Similarly, S-HELP²⁶ project aims to strengthen decision-making processes during emergencies by simulating real-world crisis scenarios. By developing a comprehensive framework and DSS, S-HELP improves collaboration across agencies and enhances the overall resilience of health services. The tools and frameworks developed in both IMPRESS and S-HELP are designed for application across Europe, ensuring that the solutions are adaptable to various healthcare systems. These projects mark important steps toward improving intra- and interoperability between healthcare providers and stakeholders, advancing the goal of a more unified and resilient European healthcare system.²⁷

Another key challenge identified in Chapter 2 is the declining number of volunteers and the growing informality of community responses during crises. The projects ENGAGE²⁸ and BuildERS²⁹ tackle this issue by focusing on educating and empowering communities to improve disaster resilience. ENGAGE examined past crises to understand the role of citizens in emergency responses, proposing strategies that strengthen the collaboration between the public and formal responders like authorities and rescue teams. This approach aimed to equip

²⁰ <https://safecare-project.eu/>

²¹ Dupont, G. et al. (2020).

²² https://riskncrisis.wordpress.com/nowater_en/

²³ Joel, E. et al. (2024).

²⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/608078/reporting>

²⁵ Liapis, A. et al. (2015).

²⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/607865/reporting/es>

²⁷ Collins, M. et al. (2016).

²⁸ <https://www.project-engage.eu/>

²⁹ <https://buildersproject.eu/>

communities with the necessary skills to respond more effectively to disasters. On the other hand, BuildERS leveraged the power of social media and emerging technologies to enhance risk awareness and preparedness among vulnerable populations. By developing policy recommendations for stakeholders, the project helped ensure that new technologies are used to improve resilience at both community and institutional levels.³⁰³¹

The health sector continues to face numerous challenges, many of which are addressed in the projects presented in this chapter. While these initiatives offer valuable solutions and make significant progress in strengthening resilience, the COVID-19 pandemic has revealed ongoing gaps that still need attention. Further research and the development of expertise are essential to address these vulnerabilities and ensure a more resilient and adaptable healthcare system across Europe.

4. Conclusion

The healthcare sector, particularly emergency medical services (EMS) and hospitals, plays a critical role in safeguarding public health and ensuring the resilience of critical infrastructure during crises. However, the complexity of modern public health threats, such as pandemics, cyberattacks, and natural disasters, exposes vulnerabilities within this sector. These evolving threats highlight significant vulnerabilities within healthcare systems. As demonstrated throughout this paper, strengthening the healthcare system's ability to respond to emergencies requires a multifaceted approach.

One of the key takeaways from this paper is the inherent challenge posed by time-sensitive emergencies and the limited resources available within healthcare systems. The healthcare sector must respond quickly to emergencies, often under tight constraints, with limited personnel and equipment. The COVID-19 pandemic exemplified the gaps in preparedness and the sector's reliance on other critical infrastructures, such as power, water supply and telecommunications. As demonstrated, failures in these systems can have cascading effects on healthcare services, severely hampering the ability to respond to crises effectively.

Key solutions include enhancing interoperability between agencies, improving decision support systems, and fostering collaboration between formal healthcare providers and the wider community. Moreover, addressing the dependency of healthcare systems on other critical infrastructures is essential for maintaining operations during crises.

To build a more resilient healthcare system, it is crucial to standardize emergency protocols across different regions, integrate advanced technology, and promote continuous training. This requires sustained investment and political commitment to harmonize fragmented systems, particularly within the European Union. Ultimately, by addressing these gaps, healthcare providers will be better equipped to respond to future challenges, ensuring public safety and minimizing disruptions to essential services.

³⁰ Merja Airola et al. (2022).

³¹ Olson, A. et al. (27.10.2023).

References

- Biddinger, P.D./Savoia, E./Massin-Short, S.B./Preston, J./Stoto, M.A. (2010):** Public health emergency preparedness exercises: lessons learned, in: *Public health reports* (Washington, D.C. : 1974), 125 Suppl 5, Suppl 5, p. 100–106.
- Collins, M./Neville, K./Hynes, W./Madden, M. (2016):** Communication in a disaster - the development of a crisis communication tool within the S-HELP project, in: *Journal of Decision Systems*, Vol. 25, sup1, p. 160–170.
- Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (n.d.):** Emergency Services Sector, in: <https://www.cisa.gov/topics/critical-infrastructure-security-and-resilience/critical-infrastructure-sectors/emergency-services-sector> (accessed 29/09/2024).
- Dupont, G./dos Santos, D.R./Costante, E./Hartog, J. den/Etalle, S. (2020):** A Matter of Life and Death: Analyzing the Security of Healthcare Networks, in: Hölbl, M./Rannenber, K./Welzer, T. [Ed.] (2020): *ICT Systems Security and Privacy Protection*, Cham, p. 355–369.
- Elkady, S./Hernantes, J./Muñoz, M./Labaka, L. (2022):** What do emergency services and authorities need from society to better handle disasters?, in: *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, Vol. 72, p. 102864.
- European Comission (n. D.):** Health-EU newsletter 250 - Focus, in: https://health.ec.europa.eu/other-pages/basic-page/health-eu-newsletter-250-focus_en (accessed 23/09/2024).
- F. Beltrame/P. Maryni/G. Orsi (1998):** On the integration of healthcare emergency systems in Europe: the WETS project case study, in: *IEEE Transactions on Information Technology in Biomedicine*, Vol. 2, No. 2, p. 89–97.
- Hoepfner, M.M./Olson, D.K./Larson, S.C. (2010):** A longitudinal study of the impact of an emergency preparedness curriculum, in: *Public health reports*, 125 Suppl 5, Suppl 5, p. 24–32.
- Hölbl, M./Rannenber, K./Welzer, T. [Ed.] (2020):** *ICT Systems Security and Privacy Protection*, Cham.
- Joel, E./Krause, S./Schaum, C./Sturm, C./Jahn-Mühl, B./Rücker, N./Bäumer, J./Wienand, I./Geiger, M./Neuner, S./Bodur, M.E./Fekete, A./van der Heijden, S./Heinzel, C./Schultze-Florey, N.F./Sandholz, S./Strecker, D./Jezek, W. (2024):** Notfallvorsorgeplanung der Wasserversorgung und Abwasserentsorgung für Krankenhäuser. Strategische, organisatorische und technische Lösungsansätze, Neubiberg.
- Lawton, L. (2013):** Public health and crisis leadership in the 21st century, in: *Perspectives in public health*, Vol. 133, No. 3, p. 144–145.
- Liapis, A./Kostaridis, A./Ramfos, A./Hall, I./DeGaetano, A./Koutras, N./Dobrinkova, N./Leventakis, G./Olunczek, A./Seynaeve, G./Boustras, G. (2015):** A Position Paper on Improving Preparedness and Response of Health Services in Major Crises.
- Merja Airola/Riitta Molarius/Juhani Latvakoski/Toni Lusikka/Claudia Morsut/Christian Henrik Alexander Kuran/Kati Orru/Sten Hansson/Sten Torpan/Kristi Nero/Ago Tominga/Friedrich Gabel/Maira Schobert/Lucia Savadori/Luigi Mittone/Alexandra Olson/Tor-Olav Nævestad/Mark Rhinard/Jennifer Hinton/Margo Klaos/Marianne Mela/Pirjo**

Jukarainen/Miia Myllylä/Camilla Kattelus/Johanna Argillander/Suvi-Tuuli Ames/Emilia Valsta/Jelena Kajganovic/Venni Arra/Mathilda Englund/Tommaso Piseddu/Mohammed Ali Berawi (2022): Handbook to improve societal disaster resilience: BuildERS project findings.

Olson, A./Woerlein, J./Antonsen, S./Fiskvik, J./Elkady, S./Labaka, L./Floch, J./Hoel Fossen, M./Gangoiti, I./Manea, G./Battisti, M./De'Donato, F./Stolero, N./Adini, B./Gianfranchi, R./van der Kolff, S./Bot, M./Al Awfi, J./Wales, D./Moens, L. (2023): ENGAGE: White Paper. Pathways to Resilience: Results and insights from the ENGAGE project.

U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2013): National Infrastructure Protection Plan (NIPP) 2013. Partnering for Critical Infrastructure Security and Resilience.

U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2015): Emergency Services Sector-Specific Plan. An Annex to the NIPP 2013.

World Health Organization/Regional Office for Europe (2011): Hospital emergency response checklist. An all-hazards tool for hospital administrators and emergency managers.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

Consortium:

Engineering – Ingegneria Informatica SPA ([ENG](#)), Italy
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft und Raumfahrt EV ([DLR](#)), Germany
GFT Italia SRL ([GFT](#)), Italy
Inov instituto de engenharia de sistemas e computadores inovacao ([INOV](#)), Portugal
Inlecom commercial pathways company limited by guarantee ([ICP](#)), Ireland
SINTEF AS ([SIN](#)), Norway
Steinbeis EU-VRI GMBH ([EU-VRI](#)), Germany
Stowarzyszenie Polska Platforma bezpieczeństwa wewnętrznego ([PPHS](#)), Poland
Laurea – Ammattikorkeakoulu oy ([LAU](#)), Finland

Innov - Acts Limited ([INNOV](#)), Cyprus
Norks Regnesentral ([NRS](#)), Norway
European Organisation for Security ([EOS](#)), Belgium
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven ([KUL](#)), Belgium
Fstechnology SPA ([FST](#)), Italy
Athens International Airport S.A ([AIA](#)), Greece
Fundacion de la Comunidad Valenciana para la investigacion, promocion y estudios comerciales de Valenciaport ([FV](#)), Spain
Orange Romania ([ORO](#)), Romania
Electricité de France ([EDF](#)), France
Leonardo Societa per Azioni ([LDO](#)), Italy

Contact:

Project Coordinator: [Emilia Gugliandolo](#) (ENG)

Whitepaper Contact: [Ompe Aime Mudimu](#) (TH Köln, Germany)

Dissemination Manager: [Anna Pomortseva](#) and [Vincent Perez de Leon-Huet](#) (EOS)

**Funded by
the European Union**

*Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.